

Cyclopia maculata Honeybush

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© M. Joubert

Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.5 to 3.5 meters

Distribution:

Distributed from Bainskloof to Riversdale, Western Cape.

Importance:

Cyclopia maculata is endemic to South Africa and has historically been used by the Khoi-San for its medicinal properties. Today, it is popular as a herbal infusion and consumed locally as a beverage. This species is an important source of income in rural areas especially the Overberg region. Research has identified various health properties and benefits, but its full medicinal value is still largely unexploited.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 75.31 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 12.1 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.95 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 6.6%, Duplicated: 92.7%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 6 633.75 kilobases

Contig number: 957

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr Cecilia Bester

Agricultural Research Council

besterc@arc.agric.za

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